

General Overview Of Macau Tourism: Suggestions For Future Development

Cengiz DEMİR¹
Raci DEMİR²

Received: 24.04.2026, Accepted: 18.05.2026
DOI Number: 10.5281/zenodo.21027152

Abstract

The aim of this study is to analyse Macau's tourism, Special Administrative Region (SAR) of mainland China, with its own currency, laws, and regulations, which, despite its small size, holds a significant place in international tourism movements, and to provide a model for tourism destinations with similar characteristics. In this context, the researcher first visited Macau (August, 2025), made necessary observations, and then evaluated the statistics and secondary data. As a result, recommendations are made regarding the future of Macau tourism, which, by 2025, attracted 40.069 million tourists and generated \$34.775 billion in tourism revenue, primarily from mainland China and gambling tourism. Macau is a unique destination that blends Portuguese and Chinese cultures. To increase its share of the tourism market, it should diversify its tourism products and focus on different types of tourism to attract more visitors from nearby countries such as India (which prioritises vegetarian diets), predominantly Muslim Indonesia, Malaysia, and other destinations.

Key words: Macau, Tourism Development, International Tourism

JEL Code: L83, Z32, O18

1. Introduction

Macau, which was under Portuguese rule from 1557 to 1999, started to be a Special Administrative Region (SAR) of mainland China in 1999, possessing its own laws, regulations, currency, etc. It is located on a small peninsula on the Pearl River, covering an area of 29 km² (Greenwood & Dwyer, 2017).

Due to its 442 years under Portuguese rule, a socio-cultural structure formed from a blend of Chinese and Portuguese cultures. This cultural richness has made

¹ Prof.Dr.Cengiz DEMİR, İzmir Katip Çelebi University, Türkiye, cengiz.demir@ikc.edu.tr, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0753-1448>

² Raci DEMİR, Freelance Researcher, Türkiye, demirraci46@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2537-2439>

Macau the pearl of South Asia. Because of these unique cultural riches, it was added to the UNESCO World Heritage list in 2005. As a historic and cultural city (Chu, 2015), on July 15, 2005, 22 buildings, 8 squares and plazas in Macau's historic city were added to the UNESCO World Heritage List. Macau has a unique historical past that led to its inclusion in the UNESCO World Heritage List (Chung, 2009). This recognition has added a distinct strength to Macau's tourism, contributing to its diversification (Alberto & Tze, 2010). However, excessive commercialization and tourism mobility are endangering this cultural heritage (Yifan et al., 2026).

The prohibition of casinos in mainland China has rapidly transformed this region into a gambling centre. Its main attraction is gambling tourism. Unlike mainland China, Macau accepts visitors from many countries without requiring a visa. Macau is under pressure due to its small area, large population, and excessive tourism. Casino-focused tourism and the housing needs of the local population are causing damage to historical, cultural, and environmental resources that need to be protected.

The development plan implemented in 2016 is contributing to Macau's progress towards becoming an international tourism city by improving tourism infrastructure and developing gambling tourism and other types of tourism (IPIM, 2019). As seen in Table 1, Macau ranked 4th among the most visited cities in the World in 2025 with 19.7 million visitors (Euromonitor International, 2025).

Table 1. Top 10 most visited cities in 2025 in the World

1	Bangkok	30.3
2	Hong Kong	23.3
3	London	22.7
4	Macau	19.7
5	İstanbul	19.7
6	Dubai	19.5
7	Mecca	18.7
8	Antalya	18.6
9	Paris	18.2
10	Kuala Lumpur	17.3

Source: Euromonitor International, Top 100 City Destinations Index 2025: Driving Growth and Innovation, retrieved 04.20.2026

2. Literature Review

Macau is a hub of diverse cultures. You can visit churches dating back to the Portuguese era alongside Chinese temples. Just as Istanbul serves as a bridge between Asia and Europe, it's possible to see Eastern and Western elements blended in Macau. The richness of Macau's culture, a blend of Chinese and Portuguese influences, can be seen in its unique architecture and diverse cuisine.

Some of the main attractions include: Macau Tower, Ruins of St. Paul's (Figure 3), St. Dominic's Church (Figure 2) Senado Square, Cotai Strip, Ma Kok Miu Temple, Macau Science Centre, and Grand Lisboa Casino (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Grand Lisboa
(Source by Authors)

Figure 2. St. Dominic's
Church (Source by Authors)

Figure 3. Ruins of St. Paul
(Source by Authors)

Figure 4. The Parisian
(Source by Authors)

Year-round events, festivals, and most importantly, the abundance of sunny days and almost no winter due to its location in South Asia, contribute to the year-round tourism season. The SAR structure, which was annexed to mainland China in 1999, has significantly increased tourism investments since then. Thematic hotels (The Parisian, (Figure 4) etc.), casinos, and show and entertainment centres allow tourists to find the services they desire in a small area, saving them time. In addition to modern facilities, structures preserving local cultures are particularly attractive to those travelling for cultural heritage tourism. Economic and technological developments in mainland China also have a significant impact on Macau. For example, the world's longest bridge, made by China, at 55 km, rapidly connects

Hong Kong and Macau (in approximately 45 minutes). This makes it easier for visitors from Hong Kong to also visit Macau. On the other hand, Hong Kong's prominence as a port city has led Macau to prioritise tourism to increase its revenue. Its border with mainland China, with its 1.5 billion population, is the main reason why most tourists come from China. The prohibition of gambling in China makes Macau an attractive destination for those seeking games of chance. Chinese tourists choose Macau over Europe or other parts of the world because it is more economical and close its culture. Some other recent literature related to Macau tourism is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Studies on Macau Tourism

Authors	Method/Research Area	Purpose
Ren, et al. (2024).	Qualitative/Food Tourism	An in-depth exploration of post-colonial Macao cuisine.
Basnyat, & Ho, (2022).	Qualitative/Food Tourism, Tourist Experiences	to gain an in-depth understanding and the perspective of tourists on how food created their experiences.
Wan, & Choi, (2022).	Quantitative/Food Tourism, Food Image	to understand food tourists in comparison with nonfood tourists to Macao, China
Li, Kong, & Yang, (2021).	Quantitative/Food Tourism,	to investigate the authenticity-nostalgia nexus in food tourism experiences.
McCartney, Wang, & Peng, (2025).	Qualitative/Medical Tourism	To examine the introduction and role of traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) within Macao's new medical tourism (MT) initiative.
Zhuang, et al. (2025).	A Mixed- Methods/ Health Tourism	to examine the potential for Macao to develop as a health tourism destination.
Liu et al. (2024).	Qualitative/Health Tourism	to explore the potential of developing health tourism.
Huang et al. (2026).	Qualitative/Heritage Tourism	to take the architectural heritage of Macau's A-Ma Temple as an example to conduct a systematic study of the island city's heritage space.
Jia et al. (2024).	A Mixed- Methods/ Heritage Tourism, Tourist Experiences.	to evaluate the image and perceptual characteristics of World Heritage tourist sites.
Ly, & Tan, (2023).	Qualitative/Religious Tourism	to explore temple keepers' services and roles in Macao's temple site management and visitor experience.
Tang, (2025).	Quantitative/Gambling Industry	to examine the impact of regional and global uncertainty on Macao's gambling industry.

Luo, Lam, & Fan, (2018).	Quantitative/Entertainment Tourism	to develop a scale to measure entertainment tourism experience in Macau from the consumers' perspective.
Luo, Lam, & Ye, (2019).	Qualitative/Entertainment Tourism	to discover the barriers for the development of entertainment tourism in Macau from the industry's perspective.
Greenwood, & Dwyer, (2017).	Conceptual Study/Gambling	to examine the impacts and development strategies of gambling-related tourism in Macau.
Sheng, & Gu, (2018).	Qualitative/Gaming Industry	to investigate the evolution of Macau's gaming industry and its effects on local economic development.
Songhong, & Jian, (2021).	Qualitative/Convention Tourism	to explore the barriers to the development of convention tourism in Macau.
Yifan et al. (2026).	Quantitative/Heritage Tourism	to propose a theory of cultural genes that encompasses both tangible and intangible cultural elements.

Source: Prepared by Authors

3. Methodology

This study utilized qualitative research methods, specifically literature review and field observation. As part of this, a visit was made to Macau in August 2025, during which tourist attractions were visited. A comprehensive literature review was conducted to support the information obtained.

4. Evaluation of Research Findings

Macau's international tourist numbers and tourism revenues are seen in Table 3. As seen in Table 3, the number of visitors to Macau in 2025 reached 40,069,360, a 14.7% increase compared to the previous year. 58.7% of these were day visitors, and 41.3% were overnight visitors. The average length of stay was 1.1 days. In 2025, the number of rooms increased by 4.9% compared to the previous year, reaching 45,165. The occupancy rate was 89.4%, exceeding the international average, which was about 60-63 %. Scientific studies show that MICE (Meeting, Incentives, Conferences, Exhibitions) tourism has become a growing market in recent times (Lee & Kang, 2014). MICE tourism is one of the fastest-growing sectors in the hospitality industry and attracts millions of high spending tourists (Weber & Roehl, 2001).

Therefore, the topic of convention tourism has been the subject of much research. Conventions also stimulate many sub-sectors such as meeting facilities, accommodation facilities, food, transportation, and tourism activities (tours, shopping, etc.), and attract high spending guests to the region. This leads to the

development of a positive perception of convention tourism and tourists by the local community (Han & Hwang, 2017). Convention tourism is also very important for Macau. Therefore, the Macau Special Administrative Region Tourism Bureau, convention associations, and other stakeholders should cooperate within an official body to monitor the development of the convention tourism in Macau and enhance their advantages in a highly competitive environment (Songhong & Jian, 2021).

Especially since 2002, many sectors such as exhibitions, cultural entertainment, and food and beverage have become priority sectors in Macau's economic development strategy as part of its tourism product diversification (Sheng & Gu, 2018). In Table 3, the number of MICE activities increased by 22.1% compared to the previous year, reaching 1861, and the number of participants rose to 1,472,983 (+10.7%) in 2025. These figures demonstrate Macau's emphasis on congress tourism. As participation in congress tourism increases, the average number of nights stayed in Macau may also increase. Studies have shown that the most significant obstacles to the development of convention tourism in Macau include the economy, inadequate infrastructure, human resources, tourism policies, and transportation (Songhong & Jian, 2021). Addressing and improving these shortcomings will significantly contribute to the development of convention tourism.

As previously mentioned, Macau has become a centre for gambling tourism (Mills & Law, 2004). Macau is often referred to as "Asia's Las Vegas" and is the only place in China where gambling is legal (Wan, 2013). Total visitor spending in 2025 (Table 3) reached \$34,775.8 billion (+9.0%). Gambling tourists accounted for the largest share with 24,760.5 million (+10.0%). Excessive tourism development, and specifically gambling tourism, has transformed Macau into a global gambling and tourism centre like Las Vegas. However, this development has also brought with it threats such as excessive housing price increases and environmental pollution (Li & Wan, 2013).

Table 3. Macau Tourism Statistics (2024-2025)

Indicators	2024	2025
Visitor Arrivals		
Total Arrivals	34,928,650 (+23.8%)	40,069,360 (+14.7%)
Same Day Visitors	18,884,882 (54.1%)	23,524,943 (58.7%)
Overnight Stay Visitors	16,043,768 (45.9%)	16,544,417 (41.3%)
Total Visitors Length of Stay (Day)	1.2 (-0.1)	1.1 (-0.1)
Hotel Industry		
Number of Rooms	43,044 (-7.8%)	45,165 (+4.9%)
Occupancy Rate (%)	86.3 (+4.8)	89.4 (+3.1)
MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Exhibitions)		
Number of Events	1,524 (+31.4%)	1,861 (+22.1%)
Number of Participants	1,330,088 (-17.3%)	1,472,983 (+10.7%)
Expenditure (Billion USD)		
Total Visitor Expenditure	31,899.1 (+17.2%)	34,775.8 (+9.0%)
Gaming Expenses	22,479.4 (+22.0%)	24,760.5 (+10.0%)
Other Expenses	9,419.8 (+5.8%)	10,015.3 (+6.3%)

Source: Macao Government Tourism Office, Retrieved: 04.20.2026

Looking at the nationalities of tourists visiting Macau (Table 4), a significant majority come from mainland China, Hong Kong, and Taiwan. Economic developments in mainland China have increased tourism demand for Macau (Jinquan, Wenjin, & Zhigang, 2024). The Great Chinese Market is a significant portion of tourists visiting Macau (Pang, Law, & Fong, 2019).

Table 4. Visitor Arrivals by Place of Issue of Travel Document 2025 January – December

Rank	Place Of Issue Of Travel Document	Total	% Share
1	Chinese Mainland	29,017,164	72.4
2	Hong Kong SAR	7,300,582	18.2
3	Taiwan Region	996,140	2.5
4	Republic of Korea	547,638	1.4
5	Philippines	540,284	1.4
...	Other Countries		4.1

Source: Macau Government Tourism Office, retrieved: 04.20.2026.

It is a concern that it does not attract enough tourists from neighbouring countries like India (with a population of approximately 1.47 billion) and Indonesia (with a population of 293.6 million). While gambling is illegal in India, cultural differences suggest that Indian tourists do not prefer Macau. Indian food culture is largely vegetarian, leading tourists to prefer destinations like Singapore and Dubai. When political tensions and other factors are added, it is clear that Macau does not attract enough tourists from India and Indonesia, two of the world's most populous countries. Indonesian visitors, who have the world's largest Muslim population, prefer destinations like Singapore and Dubai, where they can find abundant halal food. Macau's cuisine is predominantly Portuguese and Chinese, which further explains its inability to attract many tourists from neighbouring countries.

On the other hand, its limited area of only 32.8 square kilometres strains and exceeds its carrying capacity, leading to a decline in visitors' holiday experiences, social pressure, and environmental degradation (Greenwood & Dwyer, 2017; Yu & Zhuoyu, 2024). Due to its limited geographical area, Macau's tourism infrastructure faces significant environmental pressures, and the scope of resource utilisation is restricted, further exacerbating ecological problems (Shi et al., 2019; McDowall & Choi, 2010). Environmental degradation and pollution damage Macau's tourism reputation, negatively impacting tourists' destination choices and hindering the revitalisation of the tourism economy (Joye, 2017). The absence of Disneyland-like attractions in Macau, coupled with its image as a gambling hub, leads families to choose other destinations. The scarcity of direct flights and insufficient promotion are other contributing factors affecting Macau's tourism development negatively.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Macau is a unique destination that blends Portuguese and Chinese cultures. While it receives most of its visitors from mainland China, its image as a casino centre means it primarily hosts short-term visitors. To increase its share of the tourism market, it should diversify its tourism offerings and focus on different types of tourism to attract more visitors from nearby Indian markets (which prioritise vegetarian diets), predominantly Muslim Indonesia, Malaysia, and other nearby destinations. Looking to the future, Macau has positioned itself as a global tourism and entertainment centre, setting this as a long-term development goal and striving to accelerate the sustainable development of its tourism infrastructure. With support from mainland China, Macau's tourism infrastructure has experienced strong growth and has become a key driver of the region's rapid socio-economic development (Liu et al., 2025). Given the high cost of transportation due to the distance, which constitutes a significant portion of visitor spending, Macau should focus on tourism types that cater to different cultures and lifestyles to attract tourists from Europe, America, and other distant destinations. Collaborating with airlines and tour operators that offer direct flights and conducting research in this area is recommended to increase tourist numbers. To ensure the sustainable development of tourism in Macau, there is a need for more sustainable smart applications, such as transportation sharing, Airbnb, and so on. Such applications play an important role in mitigating the effects of overtourism, which strains transportation capacity (Shanshan, 2021).

A study found that the biggest obstacles to entertainment tourism in Macau are policies and regulations, economics, marketing, management, government attitudes, expertise and manpower, facilities and attractions, and infrastructure problems (Luo, Lam & Ye, 2019).

The world's longest bridge between Hong Kong and Macau is an engineering marvel and well worth seeing. Highlighting those types of engineering attractions could also attract even more visitors!

6. Limitations

This study includes only information obtained through literature and observation regarding the Macau Special Administrative Region. Future studies are recommended to compare with different cities and utilize quantitative research methods.

REFERENCES

- Alberto, U., & Tze N. V. (2010). Tourist experience of heritage tourism in Macau SAR, China. *Journal of Heritage Tourism*, 5(2), 157-168. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17438731003668502>
- Basnyat, S., & Ho, I. T. E. (2022). Food and tourist experiences: Insights from Macau, *Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science*, 32:1, 97113, <https://doi.org/10.1080/21639159.2020.1808835>
- Chu, C. L. (2015). Spectacular Macau: Visioning futures for a world heritage city. *Geoforum*, 65, 440–450.
- Chung, T. (2009). Valuing heritage in Macau: On contexts and processes of urban conservation. *Journal of Current Chinese Affairs*, 38, 129–160.
- Euromonitor International. (2025). Top 100 City Destinations Index 2025: Driving Growth and Innovation. Retrieved April 20, 2026, from <https://www.euromonitor.com/article/top-100-city-destinations-index-2025-driving-growth-and-innovation>
- Greenwood, V. A., & Dwyer, L. (2017). Reinventing Macau tourism: Gambling on creativity?. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 20(6), 580-602.
- Han, H., & Hwang, J. (2017). What motivates delegates' conservation behaviours while attending a convention?. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 34(1), 82–98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10548408.2015.1130111>
- Huang, L., Chen, Y., Chen, Y., Lin, H., & Hou, Z. (2026). Conservation of island city heritage site: a study of the spatial practices of A-Ma Temple heritage site in Macau, *Journal of Asian Architecture and Building Engineering*, 25:2, 918-941, DOI: 10.1080/13467581.2025.2472708
- IPIM. (2019). Macao emerges as a major MICE destination in the Asia-Pacific region. Retrieved May 20, 2020, from

<https://m.ipim.gov.mo/en/publication/focus/macao-emerges-as-major-mice-destination-in-asia-pacific-region/>

- Jia, M., Feng, J., Chen, Y., & Zhao, C. (2024). Visual analysis of social media data on experiences at a World Heritage tourist destination: Historic centre of Macau. *Buildings*, 14, 2188. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings14072188>
- Jinquan, Z., Wenjin, H., & Zhigang, Z. (2024). Tourism industrial convergence effect: Insights from tourists visiting Macao. *Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development*, 8(14), 7080, 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.24294/jipd7080>
- Joye, J.F. (2018). Tourism development and adaptation to climate change through legal constraint. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes (WHATT)*, 10(2), 244–252. <https://doi.org/10.1108/whatt-12-2017-0074>
- Lee, M. J., & Kang, Y. S. (2014). Subject areas and future research agendas in exhibition research: Exhibitors' perspectives. *Event Management*, 18(2), 185-194.
- Li, X., & Wan, Y. K. P. (2013). Residents' Attitudes Toward Tourism Development in Macao: A Path Model. *Tourism Analysis*, 18(4), 443-455.
- Li, X., Kong, W.H., & Yang, F.X. (2021). Authentic food experiences bring us back to the past: an investigation of a local food night market, *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 38:3, 233-246, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10548408.2021.1902910>
- Liu, M., Guan, J., Ren, L., Yang, H., & Zhuang, Y. (2024). Developing health tourism in a gaming city: Stakeholder perceptions of a proposed strategy, *Journal of China Tourism Research*, 20:1, 90-114, <http://doi.org/10.1080/19388160.2023.2177786>
- Liu, X., Li, S., Zhu, Y., Song, K., & Wan, H. K. (2025). Research on the coupled Dynamics and prediction of Macao's tourism-economy-ecosystem from a policy perspective. *PLoS ONE*, 20(5), e0321957. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0321957>
- Luo, J. M., Lam, C. F., & Fan, D.X.F. (2018). The development of measurement scale for entertainment tourism experience: a case study in Macau, *Current Issues in Tourism*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2018.155625>
- Luo, J. M., Lam, C. F., & Ye, B. H. (2019). Barriers to the sustainable development of entertainment tourism in Macao. *Sustainability*, 11(7), 21–45.
- Ly, T.P., & Tan, X. (2023). Temple keepers in religious tourism development: a case in Macao, *Journal of Heritage Tourism*, 18:1, 67-83, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1743873X.2022.2134.019>
- Macao Government Tourism Office. (2026). Market Performance 2025 Jan-Dec. Retrieved April 20, 2026, from <https://dataplus.macaotourism.gov.mo/document/CHT/Book/MarketPerformance/2025/Market%20Performance%20Jan-Dec%202025.pdf>

- McCartney, G., Wang, C. F., & Peng, Y. (2025). Betting on traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) within medical tourism (MT) development: the case of Macao, *Tourism Recreation Research*, 50:7, 1845-1851, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2024.2424985>
- McDowall, S., & Choi, Y. A. (2010). Comparative analysis of Thailand residents' perception of tourism's impacts. *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism*, 11(1), 36–55.
- Mills, J., & Law, R. (2004). *Handbook of consumer behaviour, tourism and the Internet*. New York: Haworth Hospitality Press.
- Pang, L., Law, R., & Fong, D. K. C. (2019). Mainland Chinese visitors' perceptions of Macao as a travel destination. *Journal of China Tourism Research*, 2(1), 1–24.
- Ren, L., Ngan, H. F. B., Fiona X. Yang, F. X., Ka Kui Yan, K.K. & Rob Law, R. (2024). An anatomy of the dilution of a local cuisine in a post-colonial destination – evidence from Macao, *Journal of Tourism and Cultural Change*, 22:1, 44-60, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14766825.2023.2234335>
- Shanshan, Q. (2021). Smart Tourism Development in Small and Medium Cities: The Case of Macao. *Journal of Smart Tourism*, 1(2), 27-36.
- Sheng, M., & Gu, C. (2018). Economic growth and development in Macau (1999–2016): The role of the booming gaming industry. *Cities*, 75, 72–80.
- Shi, H., Li, X., Zhang, H., Liu, X., Li, T., & Zhong, Z. (2019). Global difference in the relationships between tourism, economic growth, CO2 emissions, and primary energy consumption. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 1–16.
- Songhong, C., & Jian, M. L. (2021). Assessing barriers to the development of convention tourism in Macau. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 7(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2021.1928978>
- Tang, C. (2025). Regional and global uncertainty and the impacts on the tourism and gambling industry of Macao, *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 13:1, 2566951, DOI: 10.1080/23322039.2025.2566951
- Wan, Y. K. (2013). A comparison of the governance of tourism planning in the two Special Administrative Regions (SARs) of China–Hong Kong and Macao. *Tourism Management*, 36, 164-177.
- Wan, Y.K.P., & Choi, Suh-hee (2022). Food Tourists and Food Image in a Creative City of Gastronomy in Macao, *China, Journal of China Tourism Research*, 18:2, 376-396, DOI: 10.1080/19388160.2020.1852992
- Weber, K., & Roehl, W. S. (2001). Service quality issues for convention and visitor bureaus. *Journal of Convention & Exhibition Management*, 3(1), 1–19. https://doi.org/10.1300/J143v03n01_01
- Yifan, G., Kexin, W., Ziyang, W., Yuhao, H., & Rong, Z. (2026). Identifying and Evaluating Cultural Genes in the Historic Centre of Macao: A Multi-Stakeholder Perspective. *Buildings*, 16, 1517. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings16081517>

journalssd.com

Yu, C., & Zhuoyu, K. (2024). The Tension of Tourism: The Game of Over-Tourism and Sustainable Development in Macau. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Public Administration*, 5(3).
<https://doi.org/10.62051/ijsspa.v5n3.25>

Zhuang, Y. (J.), Guan, J., Hong, F., & Lau, Yui-yip (2025). From casinos to sustainability: Unveiling the health tourism potential of gaming city, *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism*,
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1528008X.2025.2528034>